

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CELEBRITY AND NON-CELEBRITY CONCEALER ENDORSERS ON CONSUMER PURCHASING INTENTION

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ABSTRACT

This study conducts a comparative analysis of the impact of celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers on consumer purchasing intentions in the context of concealer products. In an era marked by a significant rise in influencer marketing within the cosmetics industry, understanding the distinct effects of these endorsers on consumer behavior is crucial. The research aims to identify and compare the levels of influence exerted by celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers on the purchasing intentions of consumers. Additionally, the study explores potential moderating factors such as attractiveness, brand fit, and credibility. Making use of online questionnaires, this research endeavors to make significant contributions to both academic literature and marketing strategies. It seeks to provide a nuanced and precise understanding of the pivotal role played by endorsers in influencing customers' purchase intentions within the specific context of concealer products. Data is collected through online questionnaires from 100 female respondents in Metro Manila who have been exposed to advertisements featuring both types of endorsers. Utilizing an Independent Samples t-test, the analysis reveals no significant differences between celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers across the provided factors. Guided by the decision rule, the attractiveness variable has a p-value of 0.211, brand-fit has 0.129, credibility has 0.257, and purchase intention has 0.070. Consequently, all null hypotheses are accepted, signifying that both endorsers

exert the same influence on consumers' intentions to purchase. The findings contribute to academic literature and offer insights for marketers aiming to optimize their promotional strategies in a competitive market by tailoring endorsement approaches to specific target audiences.

Keywords: *celebrity, non-celebrity, purchase intention, attractiveness, credibility, brand-fit*

INTRODUCTION

This study contributes to the research literature on Consumer Purchasing Intention regarding the impact of Celebrity and Non-celebrity endorsement in the concealer market to determine which promotional activities are well-liked by consumers. In this highly competitive era, consumers may be subjected to a great volume of advertisements. According to Hidayat (2022), the state of being known and recognized in society as a result of social media attention paid to a particular public figure is known as a celebrity. Thus, it is claimed that positive brand perception and purchase decisions are influenced by celebrity endorsement. The attraction of a product endorsed by a well-known individual was strong back then, and it is still strong now (Sarah Cavil, 2018). Furthermore, a non-celebrity is a person who is not well known and is chosen by a company based on the target market's current demographics (Rodriguez, 2015). Non-celebrity sponsors are people who are hired to promote a good, service, or cause but are not well-known public figures or celebrities. In contrast to celebrities, these endorsers could be professionals in the industry, subject matter experts, or regular people who have a big impact on a particular target market.

Obtaining endorsers can be challenging for certain organizations, as their selection can have a substantial effect on sales and audience engagement. Some people think using non-celebrities is more beneficial when using them to promote their products, while others would rather work with celebrities. However, the problem that researchers are trying to address here is the widespread perception in most marketplaces that celebrities are always more effective than non-celebrities at promoting a product. Researchers aim to conduct a comparative analysis of the two endorsers and determine whether there are any differences between them in terms of their ability to influence consumers' purchase intentions. Marketers may find this research study useful in determining the kind of endorsers that would be best for their company.

The objectives of this study are as follows: (1) to determine whether there is a dissimilarity in the influence of non-celebrity and celebrity endorsers on consumer purchasing intentions based on given factors; (2) to assess how well the product or brand aligns with customers through celebrity and non-celebrity endorsements; (3) to examine the credibility of these endorsements in terms of consumers' purchase intentions, particularly in the cosmetics industry; and (4) to investigate how customers are affected by the attractiveness of these endorsers.

The previous studies on the effects of celebrity and non-celebrity endorsements were carried out in many nations and with various consumer demographics. Thus, the results of this study may be significant from those of the previous one, which advertisers may find useful for future development. This study may help future organizations to decide what kind of endorsers are best suited to their business. Both companies and consumers could benefit from the findings of these studies because they answered some business-related questions, like the effectiveness of endorsers on consumers' intention to buy and more. The credibility of endorsers was thought to be a significant aspect that could affect consumers' intentions to buy and attitudes toward advertising.

Literature Review

According to the study of Cooley and Parks-Fancy (2019), Celebrities, social media influencers, and real-life friends all have an impact on millennial shoppers' purchases. Their research looks on how millennials use social media to learn about commercial products and how celebrities, influencers, and people they know have a direct impact on this process. The study also covers factors that promote information trust. As they used data from college students, the authors found that information from people they directly knew to be more reliable than that from other sources. Marketers should be aware that while the research indicates that celebrities and influencer endorsers may increase product awareness, consumers still prioritize personal recommendations from individuals they know when making purchases.

Same with the study of Zak and Hasprova (2020), they discovered that in today's worldwide markets, opinion leaders play a crucial role in the decision-making process of consumers. Opinion leaders influence consumers' opinions and decisions either directly or indirectly because of their distinct skills, specializations, or personalities. The influencers who have a major impact on demand trends for particular products by influencing the opinions, attitudes, and thoughts of consumers. Over the past few years, influencer marketing—a specific type of social media marketing—has become more and more well-known. The survey's results indicated that some products may profit more from influencer marketing than others. Influencers will be most influential when it comes to buying clothes, shoes, makeup, and, surprisingly, services.

Moreover, by leveraging celebrity endorsements, advertising gain credibility and enhance brand recognition. A celebrity supporting a brand, however, could suffer from any negative publicity pertaining to the star if the two became directly linked. Using the S-O-R model and the balancing theory, the study will look into how publicity and celebrity-brand congruence effect customers' perceptions of the brand and celebrity, as well as their purchasing decisions. The celebrity-brand fit and publicity were found to have a considerable impact on consumer behavior, including sentiments about the celebrity, brand/product, and buying intent of successful collaborations. Therefore, retail marketers should spend more time looking at celebrity endorsements that fit with the brand's image and can result in fruitful, long-term relationships, (Han, et al., 2019).

According to Khan, Memon and Kumar (2019), companies are compelled to utilize the celebrity endorsement technique since they can't properly engage with potential customers due to the clutter of marketing. This essay looks at how celebrity endorsement

affects consumer purchase intentions by examining factors such as celebrity beauty, believability, and product compatibility as well as perceived quality and brand loyalty. According to early statistical analysis, three characteristics of celebrity endorsement—namely, celebrity beauty, believability, and product match—promote buy intentions. Purchase intentions are also influenced by brand loyalty and perceived quality. Furthermore, brand loyalty influences perceived quality, and perceived quality mediates the relationship between purchase intentions and brand loyalty. The choice of the ideal celebrity for an endorsement is crucial for marketing managers. For different product categories and target audiences, different celebrities might not be beneficial.

Another study found that social media influencers (SMIs) are small-time celebrities with large social media followings that communicate with customers and have the power to improve consumer-brand relations across a variety of product categories. Consumers already have a trusting relationship with SMIs and rely on their content for insightful criticism and assistance. This study specifically explores if SMIs serve as a channel for brand interaction for their followers. It investigates the process of brand engagement between consumers and brands in the digital content marketing context. This project used automatic text analysis to examine over 60,000 user comments on YouTube. One of the first studies to provide empirical evidence that SMIs serve as a conduit to brand engagement through the three elements of cognitive processing, affection, and activation, (Delbaere, Michael and Phillips, 2020).

As stated by Burgess and Blackwell (2018), regarding the non-celebrity endorsers, the growing cost of celebrity sponsorships and the perceived risk of celebrity endorsements are driving greater interest in non-celebrity endorsers. University students in the USA and South Africa evaluated the desirability of a non-celebrity endorser starring in an alcohol advertisement, as well as their desire to be friends with her and agree with her actions. The findings imply that value priorities both directly and indirectly affect the opinions of non-celebrity endorsers. More precisely, perceived beauty supported Kelman's claims by partially mediating the impact of value priorities. Values seem to be more helpful in assessing a non-celebrity endorser's behavior than attractiveness when it comes to customers' willingness to interact with them.

In another aspect a study was conducted by Kohly and Augustine (2019) about non-celebrity endorsers that currently there is an overflow of commercials competing for consumers' attention. As a result, companies and brands are forced to consider how to differentiate themselves from the competition. One way they have done this is by utilizing non-celebrity endorsers for the advertisements as they put less of a risk and have fewer adverse impacts. In comparison to celebrity endorsers, non-celebrity endorsers are less expensive, are free of the danger of scandals, and are only able to promote a single product or brand. As a result, the audience views them as more relatable.

Also, based on the study of Tanjung and Hudrasyah (2016), it is widely believed that non-celebrities are more reliable and skilled in influencing consumers' attitudes toward advertisements, brands, and intentions to buy. The outcome derives from various possible drawbacks associated with the use of celebrity endorsement. Unknown people selected by companies depending on the characteristics of their current target market are

considered non-celebrities. Alternatively, businesses can produce their own endorsers—that is, a spokesperson—by enlisting the help of not-so-well-known people. This creates a high degree of control over costs and increases the likelihood that the endorsers and the product will function better together.

Based on Gräve, Schnittka, and Haiduk (2021), there is little information available regarding non-celebrity endorsements from research on advertising endorsements. It is of tremendous managerial interest to optimize endorser usage since different kinds of non-celebrity endorsers (e.g., customers versus employees) could have various influences on advertising performance. According to this article, there are two opposing impacts of the stated link being mediated: positively (advertisement empathy) and negatively (inferences of manipulative purpose). The correlation varies greatly based on the risk level of the marketed product category. Customer endorsements are better in product categories with significant social risk (luxury apparel and eyewear, for example), but employee endorsements are better in physically risky products (auto maintenance and repairs).

When we look at the other source of impact of consumers' buying decision, based on the affirmation of Xu, Park, and Lee (2022), customers' decisions are influenced by certain purchasing channels (online vs. offline). The study also examines how marketing firms should market their goods using different shipping options. The three studies supported the theory that the purchasing channels (online vs. offline) affect consumers' psychological distance and, in turn, their decision-making process. Findings especially indicate that when buying a product through an online or offline channel, clients pay more attention to its attractiveness (feasibility) aspects, increasing (decreasing) psychological distance.

In accordance with Catedrilla (2019), in the present, peer opinions and reviews from users of social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, etc. impact consumers' decisions to buy things online with the help of public figures. Before making any purchases, consumers frequently check for reviews and recommendations as they seek peer advice and perspectives. This study emphasized the effects of social contact by conceptualizing word-of-mouth recommendations and the role that other people's buying habits have in influencing decisions to make purchases on social commerce websites. This study was made possible by the growth of social media platforms as a platform for sharing purchases as well as for optimizing customer browsing activity for goods and services, decisions and experiences. In the Philippines, the social media platforms' proliferation opened up new opportunities for company owners to profit from the social commerce has therefore emerged as the new era of e-commerce, giving businesses the chance to grow their markets and draw in online customers. Recent research has extensively examined commerce to understand the many aspects influencing a consumer's decision to make an online purchase.

Rendering to Bacay, et al., (2022), Celebrity Endorsers & influencer endorsers, Advertising Appeal, Creative Sales Promotion(s), and Timing are the factors that were noticed. The researchers utilized an online survey to collect quantitative statistics for the study by asking participants to indicate their degree of agreement with statements or

questions that included a Likert scale. Descriptive statistics and regression analysis were used to evaluate the effectiveness of each factor and its impact on purchase intention. It was discovered that the timing of events and creative sales promotions (such as giving away free gifts, offering discount coupons, and so forth) have a significant user impact on Shopee users' purchase intentions, making them excellent resources for marketers to use as they create winning marketing plans to draw in and keep customers. Celebrity endorsers, social media influencer endorsers, and advertising appeal, on the other hand, have insignificant or have no impact on online customers' purchase intentions. Although these may not be the best marketing techniques or tools for convincing customers to make purchases, they can be useful for enhancing brand recognition and developing a positive reputation.

Another statement made by Banzuelo, et al., (2019), celebrities have participated in product or service endorsements since the eighteenth century. This study focuses on coming to conclusions about the following: analyzing the literature on the influence of celebrity advertisement on consumer purchasing performance; determining the celebrity characteristics that are most likely to influence consumers' attitudes toward being supporters, neutral, or opponents of celebrity endorsement in light of some demographic profiling variables (age, gender, course, and family monthly income); to determine the celebrity characteristics that are most likely to affect consumers' buy intentions; and last, to investigate how people see celebrity endorsements, which are now a common tactic for increasing a company's sales by influencing consumers.

Social media influencers/celebrities are increasingly widely recognized as spokespersons for various marketing strategies. These are the well-known influencers on social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Tiktok, and YouTube that are known for promoting various beauty goods. They established themselves as authorities on these websites and gained a lot of notoriety. The personal care and cosmetics industry is always changing to provide consumers with safe, inventive, and sustainable products. Research shows that celebrity endorsers positively impact the look and lifestyle of their online followers because, generally speaking, they are seen as idealized role models with commendable beliefs, attitudes, and preferences. (Krywalski, 2020).

Marketing is used to spread a variety of products and services to individuals all over the world. Famous endorsers, both traditional and non-traditional, are one of the most effective and commonly used marketing methods. Actors, athletes, and models are examples of traditional endorsers. Non-celebrity endorsers including bloggers, vloggers, and instafamous personalities are examples of non-traditional endorsers. In the market environment, brand promotion techniques are influenced by celebrity endorsement, (Nelson, 2017). Some famous people have captivating personalities, are well-liked by the general public, and have distinguishing traits including attractiveness and dependability, (Hussain, 2020). Many businesses have chosen to use influencers other than celebrities to promote their goods, such as macro-influencers.

According to the study findings, the personal factor has the greatest influence on consumers' purchasing decisions out of all the variables used to gauge that behavior. This indicates that the consumers are making purchases that suit their personalities and lifestyles. One essential component of our contemporary management expertise was

consumer behavior. It gives customers' demands and wants to comprehend impractical behaviors, to influence consumer behavior, marketers employ a range of media platforms. Each advertisement on a media platform has a distinct format that draws viewers in a particular way. The internet-based nature of media consumption has changed consumer media habits. Therefore, there is a need for a more in-depth understanding of how marketing across different media channels affects customer behavior, (Aragos, et al., 2021).

According to Castillo (2018), among the most influential consumers in the world today is the Filipino. Consumer decision-making is influenced by factors like celebrity, influencers, the media, society, and similar things. The social environment and interpersonal interactions have a major impact on human behavior, and behavioral scientists are starting to recognize this. Influences from culture, social status, and peer groups have been connected to consumer behavior in terms of purchases and consumptions. It's crucial to comprehend nowadays on how Filipino consumers operate in the marketplace when deciding to make a purchase, in particular for marketing research. In terms of product attractiveness, this conduct is becoming a global norm.

Businesses can now engage in the digital world thanks to the growth of non-celebrity endorsers. This has an effect on the evolution of social media brand advertising and the spread of influencer marketing tactics for companies. Strategies that allow for direct communication with the intended audience can be put into practice at a low cost. Gender does not define beauty. Because of shifting media and technology advancements, both gender have adjusted to the skincare and beauty industries. These substitutes have also contributed to the growth of social media influencer marketing, which is a fantastic development for companies trying to build their brands. The growing influencer marketing trend has also helped the skincare and cosmetics sectors. Furthermore, customers who buy skincare and beauty products are also influenced by a variety of elements, but mainly three; socio-cultural factors, marketing factors, and physical and personal qualities. The individuals that represent brands on social media for companies are known as influencers. Thus, interact more deeply with their clients, (Wischhover, 2018).

Prior to making purchases, consumers now place more importance on marketing and promotion methods as a result of the trend toward connecting businesses with personal values. This increased knowledge is a result of their exposure to talks about social concerns, claims the study, which polled 600 Filipino individuals 18 and older using its data-gathering platform, Hustle PH app. 51 percent of the respondents from the Philippines claimed that "woke" content caused them to become "more focused on who's selling the goods and services rather than the actual products." Agile Data Solutions co-founder Jason Gaguan highlighted the importance of these findings by saying, "Consumers are increasingly becoming conscious of a brand's values and integrity, and they are willing to make purchasing decisions based on these factors.", (PhilStar, 2023).

Additionally, the purchase behavior of consumers seems to have been impacted by five main areas. Cost, lifestyle, food quality, product choice, and assistance for local farmers are a few of these. The primary obstacles that keep participants from shopping at public supermarkets nearby are lifestyle-related ones, like inconvenience, concerns

about security, and an unclean environment. The study's findings can be used to future marketing campaigns that aim to boost the consumption of fresh fruit grown nearby by enticing consumers to shop more frequently in their neighborhood public supermarkets. To encourage people to buy local goods, the local government may use marketing techniques to enhance the public market shopping experience and evoke a sense of patriotism in them, (Pascual, et al., 2019).

Research Questions

Research question no.1: What is the respondent's profile in relation to:

- 1.1 Gender
- 1.2 Location
- 1.3 Age

Research question no. 2: What are the mean scores of concealer endorsements of celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers in terms of:

- 2.1 Attractiveness
- 2.2 Brand-fit
- 2.3 Credibility
- 2.4 Purchase Intention

Research question no. 3: Are there significant differences among celebrity and non-celebrity concealer endorsements when it comes to:

- 3.1 Attractiveness
- 3.2 Brand-fit
- 3.3 Credibility
- 3.4 Purchase Intention

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The research design section outlines the type of research conducted by the researchers. In this study, a quantitative methodology was employed. According to Roger (2015), quantitative research utilizes various methodologies and employs statistical or numerical data to systematically analyze social issues. In the course of conducting quantitative research, researchers collect numerical data from survey responses, utilizing these as research techniques to gain insights into the impact of Non-celebrity and Celebrity endorsers on consumers' purchasing intentions. This research study is a comparative analysis, as it compares two subjects to analyze significant differences.

Based on the study of Bhasin (2023), comparative analysis is a crucial research strategy that helps us reach conclusions by contrasting two or more objects. It involves more than merely noting contrasts and similarities; it also entails comprehending the underlying implications and causes of them.

Moreover, the approach that researchers used was non-experimental, as the variables utilized in this study naturally occur, aiming to compare and contrast different situations. Non-experimental study designs do not modify independent variables or alter study instances to influence respondents' responses. Instead, typically provides established phenomena, (Radhakrishnan 2013).

3.2 Research Locale

This research study was conducted in the Philippines, specifically in areas of Metro Manila. The researchers selected the implementation site strategically to ensure access to essential information crucial for the study. The researcher's choice was driven by the conviction that respondents in Metro Manila possess characteristics and perspectives that align closely with the objectives of the research study, thereby enhancing the study's validity and relevance. To better reach the expected respondents, the researchers engaged them through online survey questionnaires. The targeted respondents were females aged 18-34 who had already viewed advertisements featuring both celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers of concealer products.

This criterion is indispensable for researchers seeking to garner the most precise results concerning the influence of endorsements on consumer purchasing intentions, encompassing both non-celebrity and celebrity endorsers.

3.3 Population and Sampling

The researchers decided to collect data from a specific number of respondents, which was calculated using the G-power sample size tool. The calculation resulted in 50 respondents for each category: 50 individuals who answered questions about non-celebrity endorsers and 50 respondents who answered questions regarding celebrity endorsers. The respondents must have already watched concealer product advertisements, videos, or commercials endorsed by either celebrities or non-celebrities. Additionally, respondents must be females aged 18 to 34, residing in any area of Metro Manila.

According to Alana Li (2020), 62% of women are the target audience of cosmetics products compared to male with 38% of men. Targeting women between the ages of 18 and 34 with pertinent information is essential since they make up over 40% of shoppers in the Philippines who are interested in beauty objects. The largest demographic is made up of women in the 18–24 age range (21% of the audience), closely followed by women in the 25–34 age range (20%).

The researchers should seek respondents who have watched concealer advertisements not less than 30 days ago. Based on the study of Huebner Integrated Marketing (2023), 80% of Internet users can recall a video ad they saw in the past 30 days.

The type of sampling applicable in this study is non-probability sampling. A non-probability sampling selection process was used to choose the required target respondents for the samples that the survey would ask about. Non-probability sampling, according to Kassiani Nikolopoulou (2022), is a sampling technique that takes advantage of non-random characteristics such the availability, closeness to another location, or specialist knowledge of the subjects you wish to study to address a research topic. Techniques for non-probability sampling include snowball, volunteer, purposive, and convenient sampling. The criteria that the researchers select will be pertinent to the subject of their investigation.

In this study, a purposive sampling technique is utilized. According to the Dovetail editorial team (2023), It entails the researcher selecting the sample with a certain objective in mind. Researchers select the group of respondents necessary to achieve

their research objectives. Generally, the purpose of purposive sampling is to select a specific subset of individuals or units for examination. Respondents are chosen "on purpose," not at random.

3.4 Research Ethics

Guidelines for research ethics must be adhered to for several reasons. First, standards help research achieve its objectives, which include knowledge, accuracy, and truth. Since research generally includes a considerable lot of assistance and coordination among many diverse people in different fields and establishments, ethical norms encourage the standards that are vital to combined work, such as belief, accountability, shared respect, and fairness, (David and Resnik, 2020).

The researchers utilized the respondents' information in this study while ensuring the privacy and security of their data. Before survey administration, respondents were provided with electronic consent (e-consent) as evidence of their voluntary and professional agreement to take part in the study. The researchers furnished comprehensive information and assurances to empower respondents to make fully informed, conscientious, and independent decisions about their participation, free from any form of pressure or coercion. Committed to the principle of voluntariness, the researchers will ensure that respondents engage and contribute to the research study willingly.

Research performing quantitative research meets ethical challenges such as the need to protect privacy, develop transparent and truthful interactions, and prevent misinterpretations.

3.5 Research Instruments

3.5.1 *Online survey questionnaire*

To gather pertinent data for this study, the researchers will employ an online survey questionnaire centered on the topic "Impact of Concealer Endorsements from Non-celebrity and Celebrity Endorsers on Consumer Purchasing Intention" among females aged 18-34 residing in any area of Metro Manila.

Additionally, the researchers designed their questionnaires using Google Forms. To collect data, a group of individuals was invited to respond to a series of well-structured and prepared questions. The questionnaire is divided into four categories, each assessing the influence that celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers have on customer purchasing intentions regarding specific variables: attractiveness, brand fit, credibility, and purchase intention.

3.5.2 *Likert scale*

In answering a questionnaire on a Likert scale, respondents indicate their level of agreement with the statements. The Likert scale created by the researchers comprises four components. The items are presented in a table, and respondents choose their responses by selecting the relevant tick box next to each column representing the scale of 'strongly agree,' 'agree,' 'disagree,' and 'strongly disagree.' These scales are utilized to measure consumers' perceptions of purchasing intentions.

3.6 Data Collection

According to Bhandari (2020), data collection is the methodical process of conducting measurements or observations. The researchers conducted a call for respondents by posting it using different social media platforms such as e-mail, Facebook, messenger, and Instagram. Before they proceeded to survey, 50 female respondents for each comparative topic; celebrity and non-celebrity were asked whether they had watched any advertisement regarding concealer endorsement/s in the past 30 days.

Next, the researchers conducted a primary interview using an online questionnaire to inquire about their selected respondents' views on their study. Before the survey, respondents provided consent and underwent screening based on the same criteria the researchers used to ensure accurate results and relevant findings. Respondents who did not meet the standards set by the researchers were excluded.

Using raw scores, researchers easily collected the data. Furthermore, by identifying these factors, the researchers aim to achieve accuracy in understanding the impact of concealer endorsements from both non-celebrity and celebrity endorsers on consumer decision-making among females aged 18-34 residing in any area of Metro Manila. Respondents were obtained through the use of web-based survey platforms, particularly Google Forms.

3.7 Data Analysis

The data analysis section focuses on the specific procedures and strategies used to compare and analyze the collected data. This includes a variety of steps leading to the study's conclusions or results and helping the researchers determine which of the two variables, Celebrities or Non-celebrity endorsers, has a greater impact on consumer purchasing intentions when it comes to concealer cosmetics.

SPSS, or the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, was employed by the researchers to derive the results. It is efficient software that performs advanced statistical data analysis and is widely used by researchers, including market researchers and survey organizations. In a study comparing two variables, a T-test must be conducted. According to Bevans (2020), the T-test is a statistical test that contrasts the means of two groups. It is commonly used in hypothesis testing to determine whether two groups differ or whether a procedure or treatment has an impact on the population of interest. Researchers should use a specific type of T-test.

According to Statistics Resources (n.d.), the Independent Samples t-test is used to compare two sample means from unrelated groups, where different people give ratings for each category. The purpose of this test is to determine if there is a difference between the two variables.

RESULTS

4.1 Table 1: Demographic Profile

Age	Gender	Locale	Frequency	Percentage
18-34 years old	Female	Metro Manila	100	100%

The 100 respondents in this survey are female residents from Metro Manila who were selected to form the entire research study sample. They range in age from 18 to 34, comprising the 100% sample for this research paper.

4.2 Table 2: Group Statistics

Endorsers	Attractiveness	Brand-fit	Credibility	Purchase Intention
Celebrity	3.29	3.34	3.20	3.34
Non-celebrity	3.16	3.21	3.09	3.17

Included in the group statistics are the means of both celebrity and non-celebrity under four (4) given factors: attractiveness, brand fit, credibility, and purchase intention. Each factor includes 50 respondents.

For Attractiveness, the mean for celebrity endorsers is 3.29, while for non-celebrity endorsers, it is 3.16. Consequently, in the Attractiveness variable, based on their means, celebrity endorsers have a higher impact than non-celebrity endorsers.

For brand fit, the mean for celebrity endorsers is 3.34, and for non-celebrity endorsers, it is 3.21. Consequently, in the Brand-fit variable, based on their means, celebrity endorsers have a higher impact than non-celebrity endorsers.

Moreover, for Credibility, the mean for celebrity endorsers is 3.20, and for non-celebrity endorsers, it is 3.09. Consequently, in the Credibility variable, based on their means, celebrity endorsers have a higher impact than non-celebrity endorsers.

Lastly, for Purchase Intention, the mean for celebrity endorsers is 3.34, and for non-celebrity endorsers, it is 3.17. As a result, in the Purchase Intention variable, based on their means, celebrity endorsers have a higher impact than non-celebrity endorsers.

4.2 Table 3: Independent Samples T-test

Variable	P-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Attractiveness and Purchasing Intention	0.211	<i>Accept Ho1:</i> There are no significant differences among Celebrity and Non-celebrity endorsers in terms of attractiveness.

The table above statistically identifies the influence of celebrity and non-celebrity attractiveness on purchasing intentions. The result is interpreted through the use of an independent samples t-test. The null hypothesis is accepted based on the obtained p-

value of 0.211. This result aligns with the decision rule that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, and vice versa. Therefore, there are no significant differences between celebrity and non-celebrity advertisers in terms of attractiveness. This implies that both celebrity and non-celebrity attractiveness are impactful to consumers and beneficial in convincing the audience to pay attention to concealer advertisements.

Table 3.2: Brand-fit

Variable	P-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Brand-fit and Purchasing Intention	0.129	<i>Accept Ho2:</i> There are no significant differences among Celebrity and Non- celebrity endorsers in terms of brand-fit.

The table shown above statistically identifies the influence of celebrity and non-celebrities' brand-fit on purchasing intentions. The result is interpreted through the use of an independent samples t-test. The null hypothesis is accepted based on the obtained p-value of 0.129. This result aligns with the decision rule that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, and vice versa. Therefore, there are no significant differences between celebrity and non-celebrity advertisers in terms of brand fit. This implies that both celebrity and non-celebrity brand-fit are impactful to consumers and beneficial in convincing the audience to pay attention to concealer advertisements.

Table 3.3: Credibility

Variable	P-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Credibility and Purchasing Intention	0.257	<i>Accept Ho3:</i> There are no significant differences among Celebrity and Non- celebrity endorsers in terms of credibility.

The table shown above statistically identifies the influence of celebrity and non-celebrities' credibility on purchasing intentions. The result is interpreted through the use of an independent samples t-test. The null hypothesis is accepted based on the obtained p-value of 0.257. This result aligns with the decision rule that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, and vice versa. Therefore, there are no significant differences between celebrity and non-celebrity advertisers in terms of credibility. In other words, both subjects—celebrity and non-celebrity credibility—are impactful to consumers. Their credibility is beneficial in convincing the audience to pay attention to concealer advertisements.

Table 3.4: Purchase Intention

Variable	P-value	Decision Rule and Interpretation
Purchasing Intention	0.070	<i>Accept Ho4:</i> There are no significant differences among Celebrity and Non- celebrity endorsers in terms of purchase intention.

The table shown above statistically identifies the influence of celebrities and non-celebrities on purchasing intentions. The result is interpreted through the use of an independent samples t-test. The null hypothesis is accepted based on the obtained p-value of 0.70. This result aligns with the decision rule that advises researchers to accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, and vice versa. Therefore, there are no significant differences between celebrity and non-celebrity advertisers in terms of purchase intention. In other words, both subjects—celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers—are impactful to consumers. The information and approach of endorsers are useful in capturing the purchase intention of consumers.

DISCUSSION

This section provides in-depth insights into the research output-based conclusions, the study's limitations, the synthesis of the current study's findings and implications, and potential next steps. In this section, the researchers delve into discussions surrounding each set of results, with a specific focus on the mean and standard deviation of the two comparative topics: celebrities and non-celebrities, each with 50 respondents.

Starting with the attractiveness variable, celebrities have a mean of 3.2900, while non-celebrities scored 3.1550. These figures indicate that celebrity endorsers exert a more significant impact on consumers in terms of attractiveness.

Moving on to the brand-fit variable, celebrities garnered a mean of 3.3400, surpassing the 3.2050 mean for non-celebrities. These results suggest that celebrity endorsers have a more substantial influence on brand fit compared to their non-celebrity counterparts.

The discussion proceeds to the credibility variable, where celebrities scored a mean of 3.2000, outperforming the 3.0850 mean for non-celebrities. These outcomes strongly suggest that consumers recognize celebrity endorsers as more reliable and trustworthy sources of information compared to non-celebrity endorsers.

Lastly, focusing on the dependent variable, which is purchase intention, celebrities garnered a mean of 3.3400, while non-celebrities achieved a mean of 3.1700. This outcome indicates that celebrity endorsers play a more influential role in shaping consumers' purchasing intentions compared to non-celebrity endorsers.

In summary, across all variables, the results consistently emphasize the higher impact of celebrity endorsers on consumers when compared to their non-celebrity counterparts.

This reinforces the notion that celebrity endorsements have a more pronounced effect on attractiveness, brand fit, credibility, and ultimately, purchase intention.

The implications of these findings are crucial for marketers and businesses seeking to optimize their advertising and promotional strategies. Considering the increased influence of celebrity endorsers on attractiveness, brand fit, credibility, and purchase intention, businesses should incorporate celebrity endorsements strategically in their marketing campaigns. This may involve selecting celebrities whose public image aligns well with both the brand identity and the target audience.

Additionally, based on the data indicating a higher return on investment in terms of consumer impact, marketers may contemplate allocating a larger portion of their budget to celebrity endorsements. The findings also underscore the importance of crafting tailored marketing strategies depending on the type of endorser. While celebrity endorsers may prove more effective for specific variables, it's essential to recognize that non-celebrity endorsers can still play a valuable role in certain contexts or for particular target demographics.

Conclusions

This research study aims to compare two different endorsers: celebrities and non-celebrities. The objective is to identify significant differences in the impact of celebrity and non-celebrity endorsements on the purchasing intention of 18-34-year-old female residents in any area of Metro Manila, particularly those who have watched videos or seen ads for concealer products featuring both celebrity and non-celebrity endorsements.

The study explores individuals' tendencies to make quick choices and finds that consumers are more likely to select products that celebrities recommend than those marketed by non-celebrities. This tendency is a crucial aspect of consumer behavior, and the study attempts to determine whether these endorsers differ in terms of influencing their audience's intention to buy.

Additionally, the study carefully examines several factors that are effective indicators of the intention to buy. These factors, as indicated and defined in the theoretical framework, include attractiveness, brand fit, credibility, and purchase intention. Based on the questionnaire responses from selected female respondents, rated on a Likert four-point scale, and using SPSS, the researchers calculated the mean of each subject to identify which among the two types of endorsers is more impactful to consumers. Moreover, to determine if there is a substantial difference between celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers, an independent samples t-test is utilized to support the analysis of these factors, revealing how each factor affects consumers' purchasing intention.

To interpret the results, the researchers followed the decision rule of accepting or rejecting the null hypothesis based on the p-value of each variable. They accept the hypothesis if the p-value is higher than 0.05 and reject it if not. The research findings are explained through numerical data that show the impact of various factors. Notably, the

impact is reflected in the p-values: 0.211 for attractiveness, 0.129 for brand fit, 0.257 for credibility, and 0.070 for purchasing intention. The results show that all null hypotheses are accepted, as all the p-values for the given factors are higher than the decision rule of 0.05. These numerical indicators provide an in-depth understanding of the various factors influencing consumers' decisions.

Based on the independent samples t-test result, all the given factors indicate that there is no statistically substantial difference between the influences of non-celebrity endorsers and celebrities on customers' intentions to purchase based on their dependability. Essentially, both types of endorsers have provided adequate information, knowledge, and a promotional approach that could capture the attention of consumers. There is no significant difference between celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers, as both were able to fulfill their purpose by reaching people through their promotions and advertisements. Both types are attractive, fit well with the brand, are credible, and can influence consumers' purchase intentions.

However, as shown in the group statistics provided in Chapter 4, Table 2, about mean results, celebrity endorsers are more impactful on consumers' purchase intentions. The mean results for attractiveness are 3.2900 for celebrities and 3.1550 for non-celebrities. Brand fit has a mean of 3.3400 for celebrities and 3.2050 for non-celebrities. Credibility is 3.2000 for celebrities and 3.0850 for non-celebrities, and for purchase intention, it is 3.3400 for celebrities and 3.1700 for non-celebrities. The mean results emphasize the widely held notion that celebrity endorsements are more credible, indicating that both types of endorsers have a similar influence on customer inclination to buy when it comes to concealer products.

Recommendations

The following benefits and research recommendations to improve brand advertisement may be considered by businesses and entrepreneurs when comparing the effects of celebrity and non-celebrity concealer endorsers on customer purchase intentions.

Select the most suitable endorsers:

Choose advocates whose personalities align with your target market and business. Consider their present skincare and cosmetic routine. Choose brand advocates who genuinely appreciate and use your concealer products.

Enhancing advertising tactics:

To promote diversity in your ads, use endorsers who represent a range of ages, genders, and nations. This strategy will improve brand fit and encourage brand purchases by making the brand more enticing and relatable to a larger audience.

Utilize Social Media:

Utilize the power of social media to secure endorsements. Verify if the endorser has a significant and active following on social media platforms like YouTube, Instagram, or TikTok, where beauty content is widely consumed.

For future research on the influence of celebrity and non-celebrity concealer endorsers on consumer purchasing intention, consider the following research recommendations:

Extended Study Over Time:

Undertake an extended study to investigate the evolution of purchasing intentions over an extended period, considering the changes in dynamics between celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers. This approach may yield valuable insights into the enduring effects and long-term viability of various endorsement strategies.

In-depth Consumer Understanding:

Start more studies to learn more about the attitudes, values, and beliefs of consumers that shape their preferences for concealer endorsers. The research of consumer psychology may provide a deeper understanding that can function as a strategic compass, guiding the development of marketing initiatives that are both highly targeted and impactful.

Engage with professionals in the industry:

Work closely with industry experts and practitioners to acquire insights from real-world experiences and verify the research outcomes. Involvement with marketing professionals and experts in the beauty industry can augment the practical significance of the study and its relevance to marketing strategies.

By addressing these research recommendations, academics and industry professionals can enhance our understanding of the complex relationships between celebrity and non-celebrity concealer endorsers and how they affect consumer intention to purchase by providing a more detailed and thorough understanding.

Future Researchers:

For future researchers and students, this study is highly recommended as essential reading. It can significantly contribute to the expansion of knowledge, insight, and understanding regarding the Comparative Analysis of Celebrity and Non-celebrity Concealer Endorsements on Consumer Purchasing Intention.

By providing a clear understanding of the importance of comparing celebrity and non-celebrity endorsers, along with their demographic factors, in influencing consumer decision-making, the study contributes to the development of marketing strategies aimed at understanding customer needs.

However, given the limitations in data gathering, the researchers recommend obtaining information from larger sample sizes for more accurate results. This contribution can enhance future studies and benefit related bodies, facilitating successful outcomes in the future.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Guidelines for research ethics are imperative for various reasons. Primarily, these standards serve as essential tools for achieving the fundamental objectives of research, which encompass the pursuit of knowledge, accuracy, and truth. Given the collaborative nature of research, often involving diverse individuals across different fields and institutions, ethical norms play a crucial role in fostering principles vital to collective work, such as belief, accountability, shared respect, and fairness (David and Resnik, 2020).

In this study, the researchers precisely adhered to ethical principles when utilizing respondents' information, prioritizing the privacy and security of their data. Before the survey administration, respondents were presented with electronic consent (e-consent) as tangible proof of their voluntary and professional agreement to participate in the study.

The researchers provided comprehensive information and assurances, empowering respondents to make fully informed, conscientious, and independent decisions regarding their participation, free from any form of pressure or coercion. Demonstrating a commitment to the principle of voluntariness, the researchers ensured that respondents engaged and contributed to the research study willingly.

Quantitative research, by its nature, encounters ethical challenges, including the imperative to safeguard privacy, foster transparent and truthful interactions, and prevent misinterpretations. Upholding ethical standards in research not only safeguards the integrity of the study but also promotes trust, transparency, and the ethical treatment of respondents.

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Research Questionnaire:

POINT	EXPLANATION
4	Strongly Agree
3	Agree
2	Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

Instruction: Please select on the choices provided for each question whether it is **STRONGLY AGREE (4), AGREE (3), DISAGREE (2), STRONGLY DISAGREE (1)**. Check only ONE response.

Celebrity Endorsers

QUESTIONS	4 Strongly Agree	3 Agree	2 Disagree	1 Strongly Disagree
ATTRACTIVENESS				
1. The physical appearance of the celebrity endorser positively influences my perception of the concealer product.				
2. The attractiveness of the celebrity endorser affects my likelihood of purchasing the endorsed concealer product.				
3. I believe the celebrity endorser's physical appearance aligns well with the endorsed product.				
4. I am more inclined to trust a product when it is endorsed by an attractive celebrity.				
BRAND-FIT				
5. The celebrity endorser seamlessly complements the brand image of the concealer product.				
6. The endorsement by the celebrity enhances the overall appeal of the concealer brand.				
7. The celebrity endorser effectively communicates the benefits of the concealer product.				

8. I believe that the celebrity endorser genuinely uses and supports the concealer product.				
CREDIBILITY				
9. I believe the celebrity endorser is trustworthy.				
10. I am thoroughly convinced of the celebrity endorser's depth of knowledge regarding the concealer product.				
11. I believe the celebrity endorser is a reliable source of information about concealer products.				
12. The endorsement from the celebrity significantly affects my inclination to purchase the concealer product.				
PURCHASE INTENTION				
13. The celebrity endorser's recommendation serves as a compelling factor, influencing my decision to likely purchase the concealer product.				
14. My curiosity in attempting the concealer product has increased due to the endorsement from a celebrity.				
15. The celebrity endorser's endorsement has markedly enhanced my positive perception of the concealer product.				
16. The celebrity endorser's endorsement has increased the likelihood that I would recommend the concealer product to others.				

Scoring:

The **Attractiveness** sub-scale items are **Q1, Q2, Q3** and **Q4**, The **Brand-fit** sub-scale items are **Q5, Q6, Q7** and **Q8**, The **Credibility** sub-scale items are **Q9, Q10, Q11** and **Q12**.. The **Purchase Intention** sub-scale items are **Q13, Q14, Q15** and **Q16**.

Non-Celebrity Endorsers

	4 Strongly Agree	3 Agree	2 Disagree	1 Strongly Disagree
ATTRACTIVENESS				

1. The physical appearance of the non-celebrity endorser positively influences my perception of the concealer product.				
2. The attractiveness of the non-celebrity endorser affects my likelihood of purchasing the endorsed concealer product.				
3. I believe the non-celebrity endorser's physical appearance aligns well with the endorsed product.				
4. I am more inclined to trust a product when it is endorsed by an attractive non-celebrity.				
BRAND-FIT				
5. The non-celebrity endorser seamlessly complements the brand image of the concealer product.				
6. The endorsement by the non-celebrity enhances the overall appeal of the concealer brand.				
7. The non-celebrity endorser effectively communicates the benefits of the concealer product.				
8. I believe that the non-celebrity endorser genuinely uses and supports the concealer product.				
CREDIBILITY				
9. I believe the non-celebrity endorser is trustworthy.				
10. I am thoroughly convinced of the non-celebrity endorser's depth of knowledge regarding the concealer product.				
11. I believe the non-celebrity endorser is a reliable source of information about concealer products.				
12. The endorsement from the non-celebrity significantly affects my inclination to purchase the concealer product.				
PURCHASE INTENTION				
13. The non-celebrity endorser's recommendation serves as a compelling factor, influencing my decision to likely purchase the concealer product.				

14. My curiosity in attempting the concealer product has increased due to the endorsement from a non-celebrity.				
15. The non-celebrity endorser's endorsement has markedly enhanced my positive perception of the concealer product.				
16. The non-celebrity endorser's endorsement has increased the likelihood that I would recommend the concealer product to others.				

Scoring:

The **Attractiveness** sub-scale items are **Q1, Q2, Q3** and **Q4**, The **Brand-fit** sub-scale items are **Q5, Q6, Q7** and **Q8**, The **Credibility** sub-scale items are **Q9, Q10, Q11** and **Q12..** The **Purchase Intention** sub-scale items are **Q13, Q14, Q15** and **Q16**.

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